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Non-Antibiotic Strategies for Tackling Anti-Microbial Resistance (AMR) In Aquaculture

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Abstract

Aquaculture has merged as rapidly growing sector essential for food security. Due to the excessive use of antibiotics to control diseases in fish antimicrobial resistance has emerged resulting significant risks to both fish and human health. In this article we have explored some non-antibiotic strategies to limit or eradicate the usage of antibiotics. We discussed role of probiotics which stimulate disease resistance, immune system, digestion and growth in fish. Omics based approaches are important to improve our understanding of mechanism of antibiotic resistance and immune defense techniques used by bacteria. CRISPR based approaches provides excellent chance to eliminate antibiotic resistant pathogens through precise gene modification. Bacteriophages, having rapid growth rate, exceptional abilities to tackle zoonotic infections, host specific action, non-toxicity to surround biodiversity and adversely eliminating concerned pathogen, act as an excellent alternative to antibiotics. Metal nanoparticles also act as an impressive strategy to mitigate antimicrobial resistance by disrupting the structure of cell membrane and pathogenic proteins. Extracts from different medicinal plants and herbs are also effective against aquatic pathogen's resistance. All these strategies reduce our dependence on antibiotics, mitigate antimicrobial resistance and enhance aquaculture production

Keywords: *Non-antibiotic strategies, antibiotic alternatives, AMR in aquaculture.*

1 Introduction

Aquaculture has rapidly emerged as a prominent source of food, with projections indicating that fish production per capita will rise to 25.5 kg by 2050 (Wang and Cheng, 2024). Meeting the increasing need for aquatic food has led to significant expansion of the aquaculture industry since the 1980s, making it the fastest-growing sector in global food production. This growth is particularly notable in Asian nations, which contribute 89% of the world's aquaculture output (Bondad-Reantaso *et al.*, 2023).

Aquatic foods, abundant in minerals vitamins and essential fatty acids, offer significant potential as a catalyst for transforming food systems to address micronutrient deficiencies (Dien *et al.*, 2023). From 2000 to 2019, global aquaculture production surged from 43.0 to 120.1 million metric tons (Mt), marking an impressive 180% increase. In 2021, the market value of global aquaculture production reached USD 267,423.64 million, with expectations for continued growth. Projections suggest that by 2028, the market size is anticipated to reach USD 357,903.27 million (Nik Mohamad Nek Rahimi *et al.*, 2022).

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The aquaculture sector encompasses a vast array of aquatic plants and animal species (425 species). This spectrum ranges from the cultivation of unicellular *Chlorella* algae in controlled indoor bioreactors to the farming of Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) in open floating net cages (Tacon, 2020; Verdegem *et al.*, 2023). However, concerns regarding food safety arise within the aquaculture industry due to potential contamination with chemical residues and biological agents such as bacteria and viruses. These safety issues are influenced by various factors including the specific type of aquaculture, methods of production, environmental conditions and geographic region (Deekshit *et al.*, 2023).

Antimicrobial Use

While acknowledging the benefits of aquaculture, it's essential to consider its drawbacks as well (Santos and Ramos, 2018). The increasing demand for finfish and shellfish has prompted a shift from extensive to semi-intensive and intensive farming systems, chosen for their higher productivity. However, this intensification results in elevated stocking densities and nutrient discharge, leading to poor water quality. Consequently, there is a heightened risk of pathogen outbreaks due to the combination of high density and poor water conditions. In intensive farming, where disease rates are higher, reliance on antibiotics and other supplements becomes commonplace (Watts *et al.*, 2017). However, the intensification of fish farming has changed the physiological condition of fish within the culture system, elevating their stress levels and rendering them more vulnerable to infectious diseases (Dien *et al.*, 2023).

The presence of diseases among aquatic organisms significantly hampers the expansion and sustainable development of aquaculture (Sihag and Sharma, 2012). Globally, within aquaculture, there is a recurring pattern where previously unidentified pathogens emerge, leading to new and unfamiliar diseases that spread rapidly, transcending national boundaries and causing substantial production losses approximately every 3–5 years (Haenen *et al.*, 2023). These disease outbreaks have had a significant impact on aquaculture production, resulting in annual losses exceeding USD 6 billion (Nik Mohamad Nek Rahimi *et al.*, 2022).

Antibiotics serve as the primary treatment for bacterial infections, playing a crucial role in modern medicine (Watts *et al.*, 2017; Dien *et al.*, 2023). In aquaculture, the widespread use of antibiotics for prophylactic and therapeutic purposes is common practice to mitigate disease burden and prevent bacterial infections (Hosseini *et al.*, 2023). However, the prophylactic or therapeutic application of antibiotics in aquaculture can exert selective pressure on natural bacterial populations, potentially enhancing the development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria or resistance genes within the aquaculture environment (Garza *et al.*, 2022; Dien *et al.*, 2023; Roh and Kannimuthu, 2023).

These microorganisms can subsequently pass on resistance genes to their offspring and other organisms within the same environment (Evangelista *et al.*, 2022). Bacterial resistance to antibiotics is currently recognized as one of the most significant threats to human health, impacting the ability to effectively treat various infections on a global scale (Stoica and Cox, 2021; Hossain *et al.*, 2022; Suyamud *et al.*, 2023). Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in aquaculture varies across regions, with developing countries and warmer areas demonstrating relatively higher levels of resistance (Suyamud *et al.*, 2023).

Need for the Antibiotic Alternatives

Antimicrobials are typically given orally to group of fish housed together in tanks or cages, often in the form of formulated feed, and occasionally through bath treatments in enclosed containers (Aich *et al.*, 2018). These groups consist of individuals that are sick, healthy or carriers of diseases. Without mechanisms to remove uneaten medicated feed from the water, it's estimated that as much as 80% of the administered drugs persist in the water and sediments near the application areas (Preena *et al.*, 2020). Due to widespread misuse of antibiotics, there is growing global concern about the prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria (Dien *et*

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al., 2023). Furthermore, residual antibiotics remaining after treatment are often released into effluent water without undergoing elimination or inactivation procedures, thereby enhancing the spread of antimicrobial resistance within natural microbiome environments (Roh and Kannimuthu, 2023). Exposure to antimicrobials, whether during treatment or through chronic and sub-therapeutic levels, can lead to the selection of resistant mutants, a phenomenon that exemplifies evolution. Once a bacterial strain develops resistance, this resistance can be transferred to other bacterial species and strains through horizontal gene transfer (Bondad-Reantaso *et al.*, 2023; Roh and Kannimuthu, 2023).

The regulatory framework regarding antibiotic use in aquaculture lacks uniformity and is considerably lenient across countries, with many fish-producing nations having minimal to no enforcement measures in place (Bhat *et al.*, 2022). Antimicrobial consumption in aquaculture is projected to rise globally by 33% from 2017 to 2030 (Garza *et al.*, 2022). A major consequence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is the diminishing effectiveness of antibiotics, resulting in greater difficulty in treating infections (Evangelista *et al.*, 2022). This, in turn, significantly heightens the risk of disease transmission, severe illness and mortality (Murugaiyan *et al.*, 2022).

In addition to fostering the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, the presence of antimicrobial residues poses the risk of bioaccumulating in the tissues of fish and shellfish, potentially jeopardizing trade (Naiel *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, the occurrence of antimicrobial residues in both the environment and aquaculture products has adverse effects on food safety, human health and international trade, particularly impacting developing nations and countries reliant on aquaculture (Dien *et al.*, 2023). Through the consumption of contaminated products, these residues can disrupt the normal intestinal flora of humans and animals, posing potential carcinogenic and teratogenic risks. FAO reports indicate that approximately 28% and 20% of aquaculture import rejections in the EU and US, respectively, are attributed to antibiotic residues (Hossain *et al.*, 2022; Murugaiyan *et al.*, 2022; Haenan *et al.*, 2023).

2 Non-Antibiotic strategies

Alternatives to antibiotics (ATAs) are any chemical or management technique that can replace therapeutic medicines that are progressively losing their effectiveness against pathogenic bacteria as a result of antimicrobial resistance (AMR). The increasing incidence of bacterial antibiotic resistance and the presence of antibiotic residues lead to significant global challenges. Due to the clear link between use of antimicrobial and enhanced antimicrobial resistance it is now imperative to develop the alternatives for managing bacterial pathogens in animal production particularly in aquaculture. Consequently, many countries have established action plans with the goal to limit or eradicate the usage of growth-promoting antimicrobials. Attempts have been undertaken to find alternative tactics in order to maintain health and welfare of animals. Alternative non-antibiotics methods can help to reduce the reliance on antibiotics to treat infectious diseases in both humans and other animals (Zhao *et al.*, 2021; Dien *et al.*, 2023; Edeh and Nsofor, 2023). A variety of alternative antimicrobials (Fig. 1) are being administered in aquaculture and other fields, including vaccines, bacteriophages, quorum quenching, bacteriocins, nanoparticles, medicinal plants, probiotics, chicken egg yolk immunoglobulin, essential oils, omics-based approaches, immunostimulants, antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), organic acids and CRISPR-Cas-based antimicrobials (Bhat *et al.*, 2022; Bondad-Reantaso *et al.*, 2022; Tao *et al.*, 2022; Bhat and Altinok, 2023; Dien *et al.*, 2023; Edeh and Nsofor, 2023).

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Fig 1. Alternatives to antibiotics in aquaculture

2.1 Probiotics

Probiotics, also known as beneficial bacteria, are living microorganisms that can grant health advantages to their host by improving intestinal microbial balance when given in sufficient amounts (Jamal *et al.*, 2019; Pereira *et al.*, 2022). In 1907, Russian scientist Elie Metchnikoff observed that Bulgarian workers had tendency to live longer who consumed fermented milk products. Probiotics was termed as live microbes in 2001 by The World Health Organization (WHO) (Chauhan and Singh, 2018). The Greek word "pro bios" is the origin of term "probiotics" which mean "for life." Lilly and Stillwell initially defined the concept in 1965 as "substances produced by one protozoan that stimulated the growth of another." This definition later refined as "a live microbial feed supplement which beneficially affects the host animal by improving its intestinal microbial balance" (Sihag and Sharma, 2012).

Certain species of bacteria are more common in healthy animals but different species overgrown significantly in infected animals, indicating that animals with diseases struggle to regulate their gut microbiota. This imbalance makes their microbiota more vulnerable to stress and environmental influences. Similarly, some farmed fish species may become more susceptible to infections as a result of poor quality of their gut microbiome. It has been observed that a healthy intestinal microbiome does not make the host organisms diseased. However, a disruption in the microbial community balance can lead to increased risk of harmful pathogens which cause diseases and infections. Diets can influence microbiomes, such as the proportions of lipids, fishmeal, protein and energy levels as well as some nutrients or extracts from medicinal plant. These dietary components have the potential to strengthen the host's defense including both acquired and innate immunity systems (Chauhan and Singh, 2018; Jamal *et al.*, 2019; Bondad-Reantaso *et al.*, 2022).

Probiotic microorganisms have shown promising outcomes when used in experiments with aquatic animals. For example, probiotics have boosted antiparasitic activity and growth rates in Nile tilapia, enhanced growth rates and immune responses in Nile tilapia and better survival and growth rates in Rahu (Abdel-Aziz *et*

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al., 2020; Dawood *et al.*, 2020; Bhujel *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, probiotics, prebiotics, synbiotics and postbiotics (PPSP) are potent gut microbiota regulators offering significant opportunities for disease prevention as they are very advantageous. Prebiotics are traditionally indigestible dietary ingredients that selectively stimulate the activity and growth of many beneficial bacteria in the digestive tract (Li *et al.*, 2021; Pereira *et al.*, 2022). Synbiotics are the combination of prebiotics and probiotics which can be used to restore a dysfunctional gut microbiome (Vallianou *et al.*, 2020). Postbiotics are non-viable microorganisms or byproducts produced by microorganisms that enhance the health of the host directly or indirectly. These include proteins, enzymes, peptides, fatty acids, amino acids, vitamins and other organic compounds (del Valle *et al.*, 2023).

Probiotics have an exclusive mechanism to protecting the host from intestinal problems. Their method of colonization resistance prevents different harmful microorganisms from establishing themselves. A range of inhibitory substances are secreted by probiotic microorganisms including lactic acid, acetic acid, H₂O₂ and bacteriocins which impede both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. These secretions lowers the pathogen numbers by inhibiting the production of virulence factors (Chauhan and Singh, 2018; Bhat and Altinok, 2023). The protection provided by probiotics can be attributed to their direct prevention of pathogens or their ability to regulate the immune system (Jamal *et al.*, 2019). Notably, certain probiotics such as lactic acid bacteria (LAB) including *Lactobacillus* sp., *Phaeobacter* sp. and *Bacillus* sp. stimulate disease resistance in aquatic animals. In addition to disease resistance, some probiotics improve water quality, digestion and growth in fish (Bondad-Reantaso *et al.*, 2022).

Probiotics hinder harmful bacteria from adhering to the intestinal lining through a method called competitive inhibition. Characteristics considered crucial to probiotic selection are the effectiveness of probiotics to colonize the gut, cling to the epithelial surface and pathogens inhibition (Chauhan and Singh, 2018). Probiotics, particularly *Lactobacillus* strains, improve the health of aquatic animals without any negative consequences while other benefits include improved immune response, enzyme activity, growth, weight gain and water quality. They also enhance the digestive enzymes production such as protease, amylase, lysozyme and lipase (Pereira *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, Some bacteria produce substances that enhance the immune response in shrimp and fish. In general, this immune effect can be improved by probiotics in three major ways, stimulating macrophages to increase their phagocytic capability, increasing synthesis of systemic and enhancing local antibodies at mucus surfaces (Jamal *et al.*, 2019).

2.2 Omics based approaches

The urgent need for new antimicrobials arises from the rapid evolution of resistance among pathogens making it difficult to control infectious diseases. Antimicrobial drug discovery has stalled with no new classes discovered since daptomycin in 1986, which was approved in 2003. Recent progress has focused on modifying existing drugs rather than creating new classes. To address this, innovative approaches and modern omics technologies are needed to recognize new targets in pathogens for new antimicrobial development (Chernov *et al.*, 2019; Durand *et al.*, 2019).

Omics encompasses various fields in biological sciences including proteomics, genomics, transcriptomics and metabolomics aiming to recognize, quantify and characterize structure, function and dynamics of all biological molecules (lipids: lipidomics, genes: genomics, proteins: proteomics, mRNA: transcriptomics, genetics: metagenetics and metabolites: metabolomics). Technological advances in high-throughput analysis and bioinformatics have driven the field leading to broad applications in life sciences. Omics technologies are popular in research for their potential to provide a comprehensive view of complicated biological systems (Nogueira and Botelho, 2021; Dien *et al.*, 2023).

Metagenomics which studies multiple genomes within a microbial community, has gained prominence over the past decade. It is a crucial tool for exploring a range of microbiota in aquatic environments and assessing antimicrobial resistance characteristics in microbiomes. By directly isolating DNA from samples metagenomics offers insights into the diversity, functions and roles of microorganisms without the need for

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culturing them. This method can identify bacterial organisms, pathogens and virulence genes and allows for re-analysis as new genes are discovered. Due to these advantages metagenomics is promising for antimicrobial resistance (AMR) surveillance, enabling comprehensive identification of resistance genes in a single analysis (Nogueira and Botelho, 2021; Uddin *et al.*, 2021).

The entire collection of proteins that are present in a cell at any moment is called as proteome and the term "proteomics" describes the experimental analysis of this proteome and proteins which usually involves mass spectrometry analysis and protein purification. Many proteins have unique amino acid sequences among different microorganisms and based on proteome analysis there are various analytical techniques that are used to differentiate and characterize microorganisms (Janiszewska *et al.*, 2022). A comprehensive understanding of the interactions of host-pathogen and the unpredictable nature of infectious diseases demands for incorporation of proteomics and other omic technologies and computational methods. Proteomics provides an effective pathway for the discovery of novel therapeutic targets and improving our understanding of mechanism of antibiotic resistance and immune defense tactics used by bacterial pathogens (Torres-Sangiao *et al.*, 2022a; Torres-Sangiao *et al.*, 2022b).

Transcriptomics-based approaches are crucial for combating antimicrobial resistance (AMR) by providing insights into the mechanisms of resistance gene acquisition and dissemination. Adding proteomics to transcriptomic analyses enhances the annotation of infectious agent genomes, provides experimental existence of genes, delineates intergenic incidences and refines the range of available pathogen's gene. Rather than focusing on a specific system, protein or gene, transcriptomics provides a broader view of cellular activity at a given time. Through this, transcriptomic profiles for each antimicrobial may be created enabling observation of the systems that are suffered when a microbe is exposed to an antibiotic (Khodadadi *et al.*, 2020; McCarlie *et al.*, 2023; De Abreu *et al.*, 2021).

2.3 CRISPR/Cas-based Antimicrobials

A CRISPR array and a collection of CRISPR-associated genes (*cas*) make a system called CRISPR system (Tao *et al.*, 2022). The CRISPR array consists of short repeated palindromic DNA sequences interspersed with unique spacer sequences that act as a memory of previous infections by viral. (Richardson *et al.*, 2023). The Cas9 endonuclease enzyme which is responsible for the generation of double-strand breaks (DSBs) (Liu *et al.*, 2018). The sgRNA is the key to specificity of CRISPR/Cas system which serve as molecular guide directing cas9 to cutting site (Roy *et al.*, 2022). Based on its components proteins and mechanism of action, the CRISPR-Cas system is primarily divided into two classes. Class 1 degrades nucleic acids using multi-protein effector complexes and can be further divided into different types including type I, type III and type IV while Class 2 degrades nucleic acids using single-protein effector complexes which are also further divided into type II, type V and type VI. CRISPR-Cas systems of type II are more extensively studied and used to eradicate the genes involving in antimicrobial resistance because of their relatively simple and basic structure (Hillary and Ceasar, 2022; Tao *et al.*, 2022).

The CRISPR-Cas system works in a sequence-specific way identify and cleave the foreign RNA or DNA (Mohanraju *et al.*, 2016). The CRISPR/Cas systems-based bacterial mechanism of defense consists of three steps.

- i. Adaptation stage: The CRISPR array is modified by the insertion of new spacers from invading motile genetic element (MGE).
- ii. Expression stage: A lengthy precursor CRISPR RNA (pre-crRNA) is produced by the transcription of CRISPR which is then processed into mature crRNA. In this step, expression of *cas* genes also occurs.
- iii. Interference stage: It is cleavage step. The nucleic acid-targeted cleavage is directed by mature crRNA. (Rath *et al.*, 2015; Hille and Charpentier, 2016).

The mature crRNA forms a nucleic acid-protein complex with Cas protein during interference step which break down the nucleic acid near the recognition site utilizing endonuclease cas genes after recognizing the complementary sequences to the crRNA in nucleic acids. The ability to target and eliminate specific drug resistance genes using CRISPR systems is made possible due its specificity which allow it to limit the spread of antibiotic resistance and control horizontal gene transfer (Tao *et al.*, 2022).

In last few years the CRISPR-Cas system has appeared to be a potential strategy to create next-generation antibiotics that specifically target particular bacterial populations. This system provides an excellent chance to eliminate antibiotic-resistant pathogens by targeting their DNA or inhibiting selective genes linked to resistance, virulence or pathogenicity (Mayorga-Ramos *et al.*, 2023), and kill the bacteria or restore their antibiotic sensitivity (Tao *et al.*, 2022). Based on target gene locations, there are two ways to use CRISPR-Cas system as an antibacterial agent, the pathogen and the gene-focused approach. The pathogen-focused method focuses on specific bacterial chromosomes regions to identify the pathogen and cause demise of bacterial cells. It is used to treat particular infections and eradicate specific targeted bacterial strains in mixed cultures. While gene-focused strategy focuses on plasmids that carry genes related to antimicrobial resistance (AMR). The bacteria regain their susceptibility to antibiotics after the elimination of these plasmids. It has the potential to cure infections caused by bacteria and generally lower the number of AMR genes in bacterial populations (Junaid *et al.*, 2023).

2.4 Bacteriophages

Phages, commonly referred as Bacteriophages (bacteria eaters) and represented by symbol (ϕ), are natural foes of bacteria and help humans in mitigating bacterial illnesses. These are viral entities which harm or kill bacteria. Uses of Bacteriophages are widely studies in different fields like for combating bacteria that is resistant to antibiotics (Yosef *et al.*, 2014) as well as a biomarker for wastes (Endley *et al.*, 2003). A potential substitute for antibiotics to treat bacteria's caused illnesses in aquaculture industry is therapy using phages (Rao and Lalitha, 2015). Salmonids are effectively protected against RTFS (rainbow trout fry syndrome) caused by *Flavobacterium psychrophilum* which belongs to the second most frequently attacked bacterial genus *Flavobacterium* by using phages as suitable vaccines are not available against this diseases (Castillo *et al.*, 2012). Three most frequently encountered bacteriophage families in aqueous environment are *Podoviridae*, *Myoviridae*, and *Siphoviridae* (Paul and Sullivan, 2005).

Because of their rapid developmental period, remarkable abilities to combat zoonotic infections, less toxic ability, exceptional sensitivity to host bacteria and the assurance to not adversely affect the survival of surrounding biodiversity, bacteriophages represent an effective substitute for combating bacterial diseases in aquaculture (Jamal *et al.*, 2015). Disease vibriosis is responsible for huge amount of economic loss particularly in shrimp culture and to mitigate this loss a phage known as vibrio phage is employed in culture medium (Chatterjee and Haldar, 2012). The three species of bacteria which are least studied in regard to phage control are *Lactococcus* species attacking tilapia, yellowtail and trout, *Aeromonas* species attacking salmonids and *Pseudomonas* species which mainly attack ayu (Nishimori *et al.*, 2000). Numerous studies are available about the extraction and purification of phages used against economically significant fish infections and one of such reports details the isolation of an innovative bacteriophage which attack *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a carbapenem-resistant bacteria targeting catfish (Khairnar *et al.*, 2013). The *Pseudomonas* phage extracted from sewage water and purified via coal-bituminous extraction method was extensively used by researchers for biological control of pathogens. In just eight to ten days, phage treatment was able to cure the catfish of their antibiotic-resistant *pseudomonas* infestation and decrease the inflammatory skin blisters by 7 times.

Because bacteriophages are as efficient in the natural setting as they are in the fish body so using them to cure bacterial illnesses in farmed species also has the additional benefit of lowering the pathogen's ecological burden (Morrison and Rainnie, 2004). Because wide range antibiotics may kill aimed bacteria and other good bacteria present in the surrounding or inside living hosts such as intestinal micro-biota of animal, phages are advantageous antibacterial entities due to their exact host recognition capacity (Merril *et al.*, 2003). Mutations

may occur in phages just like in bacteria and these may benefit them in evolution that enable them to withstand the effects of bacteria having resistant to phages but this mechanism of mutation and evolution is absent in antibiotics (Matsuzaki *et al.*, 2005).

The first ever experiment to control the infectious bacteria in aquaculture by using bacteriophage was conducted in Japan and the bacterium used for this purpose is *Lactococcus garviae* (Nakai *et al.*, 1999). Positive outcomes of this experiment motivates other scientists who believe that the similar study can be conducted for different other species of bacteria and most significantly for bacteria of *Vibrio* genus (Kalatzis *et al.*, 2018). A large number of diseases caused by bacteria of *Vibrio* genus are effectively managed by bacteriophages. For instance, the chances of survival of *Penaeus monodon* larvae, having luminescent vibriosis disease when infected by bacterium *V. harveyi*, were 65-68% on treatment with antibiotics but these increases up to 85% when treated with a phage of family Siphoviridae (Karunasagar *et al.*, 2007). Vibriosis caused in a prawn *Litopenaeus vannamei* successfully suppressed by using alcoholic mixture of phages from Siphoviridae family and its survival rate increase from 20% to 91.4% which is similar to that of antibiotic treatment's survival rate (Chen *et al.*, 2019).

Despite its beneficial uses in aquaculture, bacteriophages applications also face a number of challenges as studied by scientists especially in case of *P. plecoglossicida* and *L. garvieae* as the identification of most efficient variant, production of those antibodies in organisms which neutralize the bacteriophage thus hindering therapy, the specification of bacteriophage to a specific variant of bacteria, the phage may act as a facilitator for the exchange of genetic material among different bacteria etc (Nakai and Park, 1999). *F. psychrophilum*, a pathogen of fish shows resistance towards the bacteriophage (Castillo *et al.*, 2015).

2.5 Nano-Particles

Nanoparticles are an effective non-antibiotic strategy employed in aquaculture to control the increasing trend of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in aquaculture (Dar *et al.*, 2020). Significant antimicrobial impacts on viruses, fungi and bacteria are shown by metallic nanoparticles as they results in cell wall or cell membrane disintegration in microbes, hindrance in transportation of proteins, enzymes destruction and much more (Nasr-Eldahan *et al.*, 2021). Aeromoniosis was effectively treated by using a combination of thiamphenicol and florfenicol without compromising their efficiency (Assane *et al.*, 2019). In order to tackle the rising intensity of AMR, the cocktail of multiple antimicrobial agents could lower the administration of antibiotics without lowering their medicinal impacts.

It has been shown that silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs) have potent antibacterial effects towards different bacterial forms which are resistant to any drugs (Prakash *et al.*, 2015). Ag-NPs, like the widely available antifungal drug Amphotericin B (sanjeman), had strong inhibitory effect against the *Candida* species when used as an antifungal medication. In aquaculture, nanoparticles of zinc oxide (ZnO-NPs) are demonstrated to reduce the development and growth of different pathogens like *S. aureus*, *F. branchiophilum*, *A. hydrophila*, *P. aeruginosa* and other species of *Vibrio*, *Citrobacter* and *Bacillus* etc (Swain *et al.*, 2014). ZnO-NPs, according to another fascinating research, produce naturally by utilizing *Aeromonas hydrophila*, have been shown to have antibacterial activities against *C. albicans*, *E. coli*, *A. favus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *E. faecalis* (Jayaseelan *et al.*, 2012).

Nanoparticles of titanium dioxide (TiO₂-NPs) can kill bacteria involved in causing various infections of bacterial origin particularly *P. damsela*, *S. iniae*, and *E. tarda* (Cheng *et al.*, 2011). Structure of cell destroyed following a certain sequence of events and also by destruction of certain macro-molecules present in organism's body like nucleic acids, lipids, enzymes and proteins when they are interacted by free radicals to TiO₂-NPs. These nanoparticles lower the neutrophils defense against microbes thus affecting immune system and ultimately lead to less antimicrobial resistance in fish (Jovanovic *et al.*, 2015). *E. coli* and *Salmonella typhi* which are resistant to antibacterial drugs can face growth inhibition when nanoparticles of gold (Au-NPs) are used to treat t (Lima *et al.*, 2013). The mechanism by which Au-NPs are said to function against bacteria is thought to include disrupting the oxidative phosphorylation process and altering the potential of the bacterial

cell membrane, which lowers the activity of F-type ATP synthase and reduces ATP production and metabolism overall.

Recently, extract of oregano (*Origanum vulgare*) leaves was reported to have excellent anti-fungal and anti-bacterial properties due to the presences of green spherical nanoparticles which are used to treat various fungal and bacterial infections in fishes like sea bass and Nile tilapia. Upon treatment with 10 μ L nanoparticles per disk, the inhibition zone against bacterial strains range from 23.7 to 31.3mm while it ranges between 11 to 18 mm in case of fungal strains (Ghetas *et al.*, 2022). The incorporation of nanoparticles of selenium in feed of *Cyprinus carpio* (common carp) results in excellent improvement in its growth and defense mechanism (Ashouri *et al.*, 2015). This shows that the mitigation of different types of pathogens infecting fish is greatly improved by the use of nanoparticles of metallic origin as they posses excellent anti-fungal and anti-bacterial properties.

The research regarding different fish disease was greatly improved by using different types of nanoparticles like in form of tubes, capsules, dendrimers and liposomes etc. However, further research is required to analyze the potential of nanoparticles against various fungal, viral and bacterial pathogens. For the better use of NP technologies especially in developing vaccines against fish pathogens more investigation is to be carried out. Future is concerned with the production of eco-friendly, economically beneficial and less toxic nanoparticles which will be used in various studies and their production is mainly carried out by employing a suitable biological method (Okeke *et al.*, 2022).

2.6 Medicinal Plants

The typical use of different medicinal plants have different benefits like improved immune stimulatory responses, bacterial infections are protected and other diseases can also be prevented. Different types bacteria *Pseudomonas* and *Vibrio* species aibe effectively controlled by marine algae like irish moss (*Gracilaria cornea*), hapoon weed (*Asparagopsis armata*) and banded weeds (*Ceramium rubrum*) (Bansemir *et al.*, 2006). The use of plant products to control fish pathogens in aquaculture rather than using medicinal drugs are warmly welcomed (Eirna-Liza *et al.*, 2018). Due to their environment friendly nature and low cost, plant based products and techniques are preferably used to combat fish pathogens and resistance (Chong *et al.*, 2020; Jeyavani *et al.*, 2022).

Plant products are used in aquaculture due to two main reasons. Firstly, use of hazardous and expensive chemicals to treat disease in culture is reduced and secondly, this reduces the development of resistance in concerned organisms i.e., fish (Kulkarni *et al.*, 2013). *Solanum nigrum* (Mako) enhance the ability of snakehead fish to fight against *Aeromonas* bacteria and death rate is also low (Rajendiran *et al.*, 2008). A study reports that the extract of chaff-flower (*Achyranthes aspera*) is used as growth stimulator and impressive non-antibiotic strategy to lower AMR in Rohu fish (*Labeo rohita*) (Hasan-Uj-Jaman *et al.*, 2017). Diseases caused by bacterial species like *Vibrios* and *Aeromonads* are efficiently reduced by using neem, turmeric, jasmine, peppermint and mango extracts (Newaj-Fyzul and Austin 2015). Plants, being rich source of biologically active compounds like phenolics, essential oils, alkaloids and other secondary metabolites etc, have the ability to tolerate non-favorable environmental conditions and infectious diseases (Varijakzhan *et al.*, 2020). Polysaccharides produced by aquatic weeds and β -glucans (β -1,6 and β -1,3) produced by yeast constitute major portion of immune boosting chemicals available in market and are given orally or via bath to adult and larval stages respectively (Bragg *et al.*, 2018).

3 Conclusions

With the increased dependence of humans on aquaculture for fish meat and other useful products the mitigation of different problems related to aquaculture also gain a prime importance. The main issue faced by aquaculture industry today is the occurrence of different infectious pathogens in aquaculture and their continuously growing resistant towards the antibiotics which limit their efficient control. The un-wise, un-controlled and inappropriate use of antibiotics to control pathogens results in development of resistance. To

overcome this problem, scientists develop different non-antibiotic strategies like use of probiotics, bacteriophage, nanoparticles, medicinal plant products and omics and CRISPR based techniques which are used in aquaculture against AMR. Although these techniques are very effective against AMR, but also have some challenges and further research is required to use these techniques more efficiently in future.

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